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THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FIGHT AGAINST THE PANDEMIC

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РОЛЬ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В БОРЬБЕ С ПАНДЕМИЕЙ

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Abstract

The article is an analysis of the role of modern technologies in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic. The article reveals the influence of Artificial Intelligence on modern medicine during the coronavirus, as well as the development of telemedicine in the provision of consulting services. There have been identified the main functions of AI: diagnosing the virus, collecting analytical data on patients, and information on the state of development of the virus.

Moreover, the article examines the work of telemedicine not only between the patient and the doctor but also in organizing consultations, discussions, and the exchange of experience in combating the pandemic. Also, there have been established positive and negative sides of telemedicine, and in addition, the main strategies of modern technology to prevent COVID-19.

Аннотация

Статья представляет собой анализ роли современных технологий в борьбе с пандемией COVID-19. В статье раскрывается влияние искусственного интеллекта на современную медицину во время эпидемии коронавируса, а также развитие телемедицины при оказании консультационных услуг. Были определены основные функции искусственного интеллекта: диагностика вируса, сбор аналитических данных о пациентах и состоянии развития вируса.

Более того, в статье рассматривается работа телемедицины не только между пациентом и врачом, но и при организации консультаций, дискуссий и обмена опытом в борьбе с пандемией. Также были установлены положительные и отрицательные стороны телемедицины, вместе с основными стратегиями современной технологии по предотвращению COVID-19.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, telemedicine, pandemic, COVID-19, modern technology, ML.

Ключевые слова: Искусственный Интеллект, телемедицина, пандемия, COVID-19, современные технологии, МЛ.

Civilizations are always evolving. The development of civilization occurs through crisis situations. In every era, different situations affect the dynamism of the development of civilization. For example, in the 20th century, there were world wars and the Spanish flu, and at the beginning of the 21st century, we had a

global crisis, depression, and the rise of terrorism. Furthermore, in the middle of the 21st century, the most powerful push is the pandemic and isolation of humanity.

A pandemic is a worldwide epidemic. The pandemic situation can occur when a new virus or bacteria

jumps from animals to humans and during the pandemic period, the new disease usually spreads throughout the world.

Yes, the pandemic has its own historical chain of development, which includes periods such as:

- Justinian's Plague (541-542);
- Black Death (1347-1351);
- Spanish Flu (1918-1920);
- COVID-19 (2020-2022).

The COVID-19 virus is a pandemic caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. During previous pandemics, humanity did not have the conveniences and freedom it has now, making COVID-19 even more challenging.

The main consequences of the pandemic are high mortality, economic recession, social unrest, mental disorders, etc. However, this is also the reason for the development of civilization due to the search for alternative solutions to new threats. Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, artificial intelligence has become an integral part of our lives, helping in various aspects of the fight against the virus.

The role of artificial intelligence in the fight against the pandemic. During the COVID-19 pandemic, artificial intelligence is playing a critical role in

the fight against the virus, helping to speed up the development of vaccines, combat misinformation, and predict the spread of the disease.

1. Tracking and predicting the spread of the virus. In this context, AI has been able to reach its full potential. The analysis of social networks, news reports, and other data on the Internet helped in localizing and identifying outbreaks of COVID-19. Moreover, machine learning (ML) models predicted the rate and benchmark of the spread of the virus, helping governments make decisions to combat the virus.

AI has also helped the medical field with the diagnosis and treatment of patients. The TASS information news program reports that “500 thousand CT images in Moscow were checked through artificial intelligence. According to the mayor of the capital Sergei Sobyenin, the program helped test for COVID-19 and identify the extent of lung damage. It helped reduce the description of CT images to 15 minutes, and the conclusion was immediately transmitted to the attending physicians, which increased the quality and speed of diagnosis for patients [1].

Figure 1. Main causes of burnout based on survey results of 15,000 healthcare workers. Source: [1].

AI chatbots answered questions about COVID-19, reducing the burden on medical systems. The healthcare worker burnout crisis has become a major concern for the healthcare industry. Medscape National Physician Burnout, Depression & Suicide 2020 published an article where about 42% of doctors feel exhausted and report the consequences of working in the medical field. 15,000 medical workers from 29 specialties took part in the survey. A Medscape report found a high risk of burnout, depression, and suicide among physicians [2].

2. Artificial intelligence in vaccine and drug development. AI algorithms have accelerated the search for potential vaccines and cures for COVID-19. In 2020, some vaccines were created and confirmed for use against coronavirus. The coronavirus vaccine has become one of the most complex drugs. The rapid development of COVID-19 vaccines in countries like the USA and Switzerland has been made possible with the help of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies. AI has played a crucial role in analyzing vast amounts of data

related to the virus, which has helped to ease the burden on experts and specialists and provided them with read-made reports and various types of solutions [3].

ML models have helped optimize vaccine production and distribution. At a given time, ML allows companies to determine the optimal scheme. The framework may include cost and service-level frameworks for the vaccine supply chain. The uniqueness of this project is that one program can include all production and distribution processes. These circuits are made possible by AnyLogic. AnyLogic allows us to combine different methods, such as simulations within one model. These models have provided the ability to make accurate predictions and make better vaccine distribution decisions.

3. The use of AI has several limitations and challenges in the medical field. We noted three main challenges and limitations, these are points such as:

1. Not all decisions made by artificial intelligence turned out to be effective because they required refinement and verification.

2. Ethics and privacy issues have arisen when using data since learning and decision-making require different types of data.

3. Dependent on humans, the solution of artificial intelligence still occurs at the level of training and analysis of the information received.

AI has played an important role in the fight against COVID-19, but its potential has not yet been fully realized. In the future, the development of AI may become a key factor in countering pandemics and other global challenges. In addition, many companies and institutes are actively developing technologies related to artificial intelligence, such as automated diagnostic systems, predicting the spread of viruses, and developing vaccines. These innovations could improve our ability to fight pandemics in the future.

The development of telemedicine during the COVID-19 pandemic. As we know, the results of the pandemic were not only numerous victims of the disease, and the economic crisis, but also an impetus in the development of medical technologies. For instance, telemedicine is often cited as one of the most impressive examples of modern healthcare technology.

Telemedicine is the use of modern technologies and telecommunications for remote medical consultation. Telemedicine not only improves communication between patients and doctors, but also facilitates consultations and discussions among medical employees through broadcasts, video, and audio calls [4].

Despite the popularity and modernity of new technologies, telemedicine has existed, according to history, since the time of the telegraph. This is because telephone consultations are also a form of remote interaction. In addition, in the 1970s, the term "telemedicine" was first coined, which became an important milestone in the history of this field [4].

However, not every technology is suitable for the provision of remote medical services, the more responsible and complex the field is, the more requirements are placed on the technical part of the solution. The requirements include stable operation in multi-way communication mode, high quality, and detailed images because the formulation of a qualitative diagnosis can affect the patient's life.

Nevertheless, telemedicine has both negative and positive sides. Negative factors include [4]:

1. Limited availability. Due to the fact that many people, especially the elderly, do not have the equipment and high-quality Internet, unfortunately, they cannot get a remote consultation.

2. The difficulty in installing technical equipment. To set up and administer the videoconferencing server, a qualified specialist is required to ensure the stable operation of the device.

3. The risk for specialists. Telemedicine allows us to examine the patient only from a visual point of view, in this regard, there is a danger of making an incorrect diagnosis, so specialists prefer to meet live resorting to modern technology in rare cases. Furthermore, not every doctor has the skills to provide video consultation.

4. Security of personal data. Many patients prefer live consultations rather than remote ones due to fear of data leakage during the session.

5. The rise of fraud. Due to the sharp increase in the use of telemedicine during the pandemic, the risk of fraud among doctors, telemedicine companies, and medical equipment suppliers in overcharging has increased, as an example in the United States, where a record number of cases have been reported [5].

In addition, experts still prove that although telemedicine has negative sides, the advantages are also present [4]. For instance:

1. Convenience and time-saving. As we know, visiting medical institutions takes a lot of time, especially if patients live in remote areas, thanks to online consultations, it doesn't take too much time and it is possible to receive professional advice without leaving home.

2. Reduced risk of infection with the virus. Remote consultation reduces infection risk for those with weakened immunity, who may otherwise be at risk when visiting medical institutions. Also, during the pandemic, telemedicine helped to avoid exposing the doctor to the risk of infection, that is why, patients used a microphone for remote self-examination (for cough analysis) [5];

3. Efficiency. Unfortunately, there are situations where emergency aid may not be accessible due to limited personnel or resources. In such cases, telemedicine can provide emergency care and ensure proper treatment.

4. Training and exchange of experience. Thanks to video conferences, students of medical institutions can follow the progress of complex operations, and doctors can share their experiences in real-time.

Thus, it can be understood that, of course, telemedicine cannot completely replace a live visit to a specialist. However, using such technology can save lives.

A striking example of the use of telemedicine is the fight against COVID-19. The sharply increased demand for professional, high-quality information and recommendations from doctors in connection with quarantine, lockdown, and the massive transition to digital work gave rise to the use of remote medical counseling. Thousands of people have been treated for the virus at home for various reasons, but their condition has always required monitoring. Therefore, Telemedicine Centers have been opened all over the world providing consulting services and monitoring around the clock [6].

Furthermore, the primary strategies for implementing telemedicine to combat COVID-19 have been established [7]:

1. Thanks to remote consultations, it was possible to identify patients who were suspected of having COVID-19;

2. Monitoring the condition of a quarantined patient using a phone\$

3. Medical care and disease control in patients with limited access to it (for example, in rural areas, elderly patients, patients with limited mobility);

4. Follow-up with patients after they have been discharged from the hospital;

5. Care and counseling not only for patients but also for the people who look after them [7].

It can be highlighted that telemedicine is a method of remote counseling that has helped reduce the impact of the pandemic on civilization. Thanks to modern technology, it has been possible to reduce the risk of morbidity.

In conclusion, we can say that:

1. COVID-19 became a challenge for the entire development of civilization and influenced the further development of medical technologies, such as the use of artificial intelligence and telemedicine.

2. During the pandemic, the result of the work of artificial intelligence was at a high level, performing several tasks simultaneously, which helped the medical staff to focus on important responsibilities.

3. Telemedicine has become one of the modern technologies whose development was caused by the pandemic. It was during the spread of the virus that modern technology showed its positive and negative factors.

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